

DETERMINING LUNAR INTERIOR STRUCTURE THROUGH LILA, A LUNAR GRAVITATIONAL WAVE OBSERVATORY CONCEPT. M. P. Panning¹, P. Lognonné^{2,5} (lognonne@ipgp.fr, IPGP, Paris, France) T. Creighton³, K. Jani⁴, S. Kizhaekke Pakkathillam⁵, J. Trippe⁴, V. Quetschke³, J. Majstorović², ¹Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, ²Université Paris Cité, Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris, CNRS, Paris, France, ³South Texas Space Institute, University of Texas Rio Grande Valley, Brownsville, TX USA, ⁴Vanderbilt Lunar Labs Initiative, Vanderbilt University, Nashville, TN USA, ⁵California Institute of Technology.

Introduction: The Laser Interferometer Lunar Antenna (LILA) is a proposed lunar Gravitational Wave (GW) observatory focused on measuring in the sub-Hz domain inaccessible to Earth-based observations due to continuous seismic noise within that bandwidth [1]. Current proposed iterations of this concept include two strainmeter-based approaches with an initial deployment with two 5-km arms (LILA Pioneer), followed by an extremely sensitive deployment with three 40-km arms (LILA Horizon) [2]. While the focus of these observatories would be measurement of GW through the response of the Moon [3], the very low noise strain measurements required would also provide low frequency measurements of seismic signals from both deep and shallow moonquakes, providing the opportunity of high signal-to-noise measurements of the normal modes of the Moon, giving unprecedented sensitivity to the deep 1D and 3D lunar structure.

Strain of moonquakes compared to sensitivity of LILA: To estimate the strain signals of both deep and shallow moonquakes, we use MINEOS [3], a standard normal mode code developed for the Earth, but easily adaptable to lunar models. Modes are calculated up to 300 mHz in a model based on the lunar structure of [5]. Normal mode summation displacement seismograms are calculated at a distance of 40 degrees and converted to strain via differencing seismograms at two different distances. GW measurements are typically compared to “characteristic strain”, calculated from the strain via the square root of the power spectral density of the observed strain multiplied by the square root of frequency. Deep moonquake seismic moments are based on [6], while the shallow moonquake moment estimate is approximately half the maximum moment estimated in [7]. All calculations assume an ideal source orientation with propagation along the direction of the strainmeter arm, and so are optimistic estimates, but the large S2N ratio estimated here suggests measurement should still be possible even for non-ideal source orientations. S2N ratios are robust enough to also manage amplitude reduction related to scattering and lateral variations.

LILA sensitivity is computed according to the assumptions discussed in [2]. For GW detection, this also includes sensitivity enhancements via multiple arms and resonant excitement of the quadrupolar lunar modes by GWs (a key element to achieve the desired sensitivity to GWs). We could not take advantage of these enhancements for transient moon quakes, so this

noise estimate is based on the sensitivity of single strainmeter arms and excludes mode resonances.

Figure 1: Characteristic strain of typical and largest observed deep moonquake (blue and orange lines), as well as a large shallow moonquake (green) compared to the expected single-arm strain sensitivity of LILA Pioneer and LILA Horizon (dashed and solid purple lines), excluding mode resonance. Frequencies of lunar modes below 3 mHz are shown by dashed red lines.

Strain and seismic noise: While the LILA performances are in principle high enough to ensure a very high signal to noise ratio, other sources of noise must be considered. These include the surface strain noise associated to fluctuations of the solar radiation and the seismic noise associated to small impacts. We estimate these noise sources and discuss the overall SNR when these noises are integrated.

Conclusion: Lunar modes below 10 mHz should be measurable at high S2N for many moonquakes, allowing measuring splitting of those modes to look at 3D interior structure. It may even be possible to measure the very low frequency (<0.1 mHz) Slichter inner core mode of the Moon.

Acknowledgments: This work was partially carried out at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, under a contract with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration. California Institute of Technology. Government sponsorship acknowledged.

References: [1] K. Jani and A. Loeb (2021), *JCAP06*, 044. [2] K. Jani et al. (2025) submitted to NASEM study on non-polar destinations. [3] Majstorović et al (2025). *Phys. Rev. D*, **111**, 044061 [4] G. Masters, J.H. Woodhouse, and G. Freeman (2011), CIG software. [5] R. Weber et al. (2011) *Science*, *331*, 309. [6] T. Kawamura et al. (2017), *JGR Planets*, 122, 2016JE005147. [7] J. Oberst (1987), *JGR*, *92*, 1397-1405.